

How to Address Open Science Practices in MSCA/ERC Proposals?

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Introduction

This guide is not an official EU Commission document, but a complementary guide that we have intentionally chosen to focus on Open Science (OS) requirements in Horizon Europe (HE) programs, with a particular focus on selecting European Research Council (ERC) and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) fundings.

The mission of the ERC is to support excellent research in all fields of science and scholarship. The main outputs of this research are new knowledge, ideas and understanding, which the ERC expects its grantees to publish in peer-reviewed articles and monographs. The ERC considers that providing free online access to these materials is the most effective way of ensuring that the fruit of the research it funds can be accessed, read, and used as the basis for further research.

The main activities of MSCA include funding doctoral training networks, providing individual fellowships for experienced researchers to conduct projects abroad, facilitating staff exchanges between institutions across countries and sectors, and engaging the public through outreach initiatives.

The HE MSCA/ERC application forms can be found at the European Commission's Funding & Tenders [page](#). It consists of two parts: Application Form (Part A) and Project Proposal-Technical Description (Part B).

Before developing the practices of OS, let us just recall the definition of OS as proposed by [UNESCO](#): “Open science is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefits of scientists and society as a whole. Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable”.

In the evaluation of proposals, OS practices are considered under Part A and Part B - 'Excellence', 'Impact' and 'Quality and Efficiency of Implementation'¹ (e.g. [HE MSCA evaluation Form](#)).

Applicants must clearly explain how they will meet OS requirements², and failure to provide sufficient details about mandatory OS practices will result in a lower score. Similarly, providing a clear explanation of how they will follow recommended practices is optional. It will not affect their

¹ This does not apply to the ERC programme that does not include OS in the evaluation. However, OS practices are still important for the evaluation considering data quality, research efficiency and integrity.

² The European IP Helpdesk recently released a guide titled “[Guide to Open Science in Horizon Europe](#)” that provides an introduction to key open science concepts.

score if not addressed, but it will boost their evaluation score if included. If OS practices can not be applied to their project, a strong justification must be provided.

Open Science Practise ²		Mandatory	Recommended
Early and open sharing of research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preregistration, registered reports, preprints, etc. 		Yes
Research output management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data management plan (DMP) 	Yes	
Ensure reproducibility of research outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information on outputs/tools/instruments and access to data/results for validation of publications 	Yes	
Open access to research outputs through deposition in trusted repositories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open access to publications Open access to data Open access to software, models, algorithms, workflows etc. 	Yes, for peer-reviewed publications and research data ('as open as possible as closed as necessary')	Yes, for other research outputs.
Participate in open peer-review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish in open peer-reviewed journals or platforms 		Yes
Involving all relevant knowledge actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involve citizens, civil society, and end-users in co-creation of content (e.g., crowd-sourcing, etc.) 		Yes

Figure 1: [MSCA-NET Policy Brief](#)

OS requirements in these programs are embedded in the grant agreement and depend on their framework (and in some cases, the specific ERC/MSCA call) under which funding was obtained. Read more about the requirements, as well as practical steps related to the publication and sharing of your research outputs.

Part A: Application form

- List of up to 5 publications, widely-used datasets, software, goods, services, or any other achievements of consortium members relevant to the call content
- Publications expected to be open access
- Datasets expected to be FAIR and open*

*"As open as possible, as closed as necessary"

How do I address open science in my proposal?

HORIZON EUROPE

Open science (OS) takes a central place in Horizon Europe and open science practices are considered in the evaluation of Horizon Europe proposals. If not applicable to the proposal, justifications should be provided so that, if evaluators agree, open science will not be taken into consideration in the evaluation.

Part B: Project proposal - Technical description

- 1 Excellence**
 - 1.1 Objectives and ambition
 - 1.2 Methodology

Open Science [max. 1 page]
How will the project implement mandatory and recommended open science practices in a manner appropriate to the nature of the proposed work?

Mandatory OS practices	Recommended OS practices
Open access to scientific publications	Early and open sharing of research
Open* access to research data	Preregistration, open peer-review
Information/documentation about research outputs needed for research validation and data reuse	Citizen science, society engagement
Management of research data in line with FAIR principles	Research output management (beyond data)
	Reproducible outputs

Research Data Management (RDM) and management of other research outputs (exc. publications) [max. 1 page]
How will the data/ research outputs be managed in line with the FAIR principles?

Types of data & research outputs	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability of data & research outputs	Costs and responsibilities of data curation, storage and preservation
- 2 Impact**
 - 2.1 Project's pathways towards impact
 - 2.2 Measures to maximize impact. Dissemination, exploitation & communication
 - 2.3 Summary

2.2 Measures to maximize impact. Dissemination, exploitation & communication

Tips Refer to relevant Open Science practices described in the Methodology section (i.e. open access to research outputs and early and open sharing of research)

Make sure proposed practices are compatible with your dissemination and exploitation plan (e.g. protection of intellectual property) and consortium agreements
- 3 Quality and efficiency of the implementation**
 - 3.1 Work plan and resources
 - 3.2 Capacity of participants & consortium as a whole

3.1 Work plan and resources

Tips Give visibility to RDM with distinct tasks or work packages

Include the full Data Management Plan (DMP) as a deliverable

Include other relevant RDM activities and budget them

3.2 Capacity of participants & consortium as a whole

Tips Describe consortium partners' capacities in open science

Refer to USent's efforts to promote & support Open Science

For more info, check the research tip:
Horizon Europe: How do I address open science in my proposal?

Source: Infographic created by Open science team, Ghent University Library

Step-by-Step

Below, you will find a step-by-step guide to help you navigate and implement these guidelines for OS practices.

Part A - Application Form

In the Part A (see below), applicants should list up to five relevant publications, datasets and other achievements significant to the proposed action. Open access is expected for the publication while datasets are expected to be FAIR and 'open as possible, as closed as necessary'.

“FAIR is an acronym for *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable*. The [FAIR data principles](#) state that it should be possible to find research data, there should be information about how to gain access to them, they should be compatible with other data, and possible to reuse. The FAIR data principles are an integral part of the work within open science, and describe some of the most central guidelines for good data management and open access to research data³”.

Application forms

Proposal ID

Acronym **Acronym is mandatory**

Short name

List of up to 5 publications, widely-used datasets, software, goods, services, or any other achievements relevant to the call content.

Type of achievement	Short description (Max 500 characters)

List of up to 5 most relevant previous projects or activities, connected to the subject of this proposal.

Name of Project or Activity	Short description (Max 500 characters)

Description of any significant infrastructure and/or any major items of technical equipment, relevant to the proposed work.

Name of infrastructure of equipment	Short description (Max 300 characters)

Application Form (Part A)

! Note: Check here to see if the research discipline offers open access to research materials. It is true that some research domains have less open access practices implemented than others.

Recommendations

³ Source: <https://snd.se/en/manage-data/prepare-and-share/FAIR-data-principles>

Publication

- Here, you should list your relevant publications. By default, they should be open access. If not:
 - 1 - Deposit your publications in open access repositories or archives, with the goal of making them publicly available as soon as possible.
 - 2 - Use open access journals or preprints in open archives to maximise dissemination and accessibility.

! Note: Publications will not be judged based on the journal impact factor⁴, but rather on a qualitative assessment provided by the proposers for each publication.

Research Data

- Same as publication, list your relevant datasets:
 - 1 - Use data repositories to deposit your research data (institutional, generalist and discipline-based):

- Generalist data repositories:
 - Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>
 - Open repository for EU-funded research: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eu/>

Note: EU Open Research Repository is a project community providing a common space to manage research outputs. Currently, in a pilot phase and expected to be fully operational in autumn 2024.

- Open Science Framework (OSF): <https://osf.io/>
- Dryad: <https://datadryad.org/>

These repositories accept data regardless of subject matter, type, format, or disciplinary focus, and provide persistent identifiers to ensure the data is preserved and accessible.

- Thematic data repositories:
 - [EU Open Research](#) provides you with guidelines on open data, software and code where you can find examples of thematic repositories that align with these guidelines.
- Institutional repositories:
 - Check if your institution has a data repository solution.

⁴ “The **impact factor (IF)** or **journal impact factor (JIF)** of an [academic journal](#) is a [scientometric](#) index calculated by [Clarivate](#) that reflects the yearly mean number of [citations](#) of articles published in the last two years in a given journal, as indexed by Clarivate's [Web of Science](#)”. Source: Wikipedia

Part B - 'Excellence'

Under the 'Excellence part' (B section 1.2), two subheadings are dedicated to OS practices.

1.2 Soundness of the proposed methodology (including interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension and other diversity aspects if relevant for the research project, and the quality and appropriateness of open science practices)

Required sub-headings:

- Overall methodology
- Integration of methods and disciplines to pursue the objectives
- Gender dimension and other diversity aspects
- Open science practices
- Research data management and management of other research outputs
- Artificial intelligence (if applicable to the proposal)

EU Grants: Application form (HE MSCA DN): V2.2-18.04.2023

Proposers should explain how they implement OS practices in their methodology and demonstrate how their implementation is adapted to their work and increases the project objectives. If the OS is not applicable to the project, provide a justification.

OS practices should be given in one page accompanied by an additional introduction of a data management plan (DMP)⁵ (max 1 page) for generating/reusing data.

Open Science (OS) Practices-[1 page]

Later in the same document, there is an instruction corresponding to OS practices which explains how to complete this part:

- *Open science practices:* Describe how appropriate open science practices are implemented as an integral part of the proposed methodology. Show how the choice of practices and their implementation are adapted to the nature of your work, in a way that will increase the chances of the project delivering on its objectives. If you believe that none of these practices are appropriate for your project, you should provide a justification.

 Open science is an approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the process. Open science practices include early and open sharing of research (for example through preregistration, registered reports, pre-prints, or crowd-sourcing); research output management; measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs; providing open access to research outputs (such as publications, data, software, models, algorithms, and workflows); participation in open peer-review; and involving all relevant knowledge actors including citizens, civil society and end users in the co-creation of R&I agendas and contents (such as citizen science).

 Please note that this question does not refer to outreach actions that may be planned as part of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. These aspects should instead be described below under 'Impact'.

EU Grants: Application form (HE MSCA DN): V2.2-18.04.2023

⁵ Data management plan (DMP) will be explained later in the document.

As seen in the [Figure 1](#), the mandatory OS practices cover:

- *Open access to research outputs through a trusted repository and open archive*
- *Reproducibility of research outputs*
- *Research outputs management*

! Note: Research outputs here should be understood globally including publications, datasets, codes, software, tools, etc.

Open access to research materials through a trusted repository and open archive
(Mandatory) [↪](#)

This part focuses on explaining how you will meet the open access requirements. You must provide **immediate open access** (no embargo period) upon publication through a trust-worthy repository using the Creative Commons licence⁶ or an equivalent open licence. You should address open access to research data and other research outputs in the research data management section of your proposal, as detailed below.

1 - Follow Open Access Principles:

- Be "*as open as possible and as closed as necessary*": Prioritise openness for accessibility, so that the research can be reused and built upon. However, make sure to not violate the privacy of the research subject and be sure to guard commercially valuable results.

2 - Open Access Publishing:

- Ensure that publications are deposited and made openly accessible through trusted platforms.

Example:

- [Europe PMC](#), for life sciences
- [arXiv](#) for physics, mathematics, computer science, etc.
- Provide details on the other research outputs required to validate the publication's conclusions
- Disseminate publications in open access journals or deposit preprints in open archives to maximise dissemination and accessibility. Regardless of where you publish (e.g., full OA, hybrid journal), you must still deposit the Author Accepted Manuscript and/or Version of Record in a repository, unless you publish in Open Research Europe.

⁶ See the different [Creative Commons licences](#).

England, J. (2024, mars 19). Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice-OpenAIRE webinar. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810347>

Example:

- Submit manuscripts to journals indexed in the [Directory of Open Access Journals](#) (DOAJ) or self-archive preprints on platforms like HAL, [arXiv](#) or bioRxiv.
- Use the [Journal Checker Tool](#), Directory of Open Access Journals, and [Open Research Europe](#) platform to find open access publishing venues that meet Horizon Europe's requirements
- Retain your rights by having the Author Accepted Manuscript and/or Version of Record under open access. See below:

England, J. (2024, mars 19). Horizon Europe Open Science requirements in practice - OpenAIRE webinar. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810347>

Keep in mind that [cOAlition S](#), a movement advocating for complete and immediate Open Access to research publications, has launched a Rights Retention Strategy. This strategy enables researchers to retain the right to submit their work for publication to journals of choice, including subscription-based ones.

3 - Go Beyond Publications (highly recommended):

- Open Access is not just for papers; consider software, models, and more.
- Share 'physical' results early, like cell lines and materials.

4 - Use Open Research Europe (optional):

- Consider [Open Research Europe](#), the EU's open access publishing platform for scientific articles as a peer-reviewed publishing service

! Note: Source datasets associated with Open Research Europe articles are deposited in repositories that meet [certain criteria](#). Articles include a Data Availability Statement section outlining where the source data can be found, including the DOI(s) and a reference with details of how to cite the dataset(s). See the [Open Data, Software and Code Guidelines](#).

5 - Post-Data Generation Guidelines:

After your project generates research data, follow these key steps:

- Adhere as much as possible to the 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary' principle, depositing data as soon as possible after production or adequate processing, with the latest deadline being the end of the project.
- Deposit the research data or other outputs in a trusted repository if possible.
- Select a repository based on contractual obligations, ensuring compliance with grant agreement requirements for information and metadata provision.
- Ensure that metadata for deposited research data must be open (under a CC0 licence) and aligns with FAIR principles.
- Provide open access to the deposited research data within the deadlines specified in your data management plan.
- Licence the research (meta)data under appropriate Creative Commons licences or dedicate them to the public domain.
- Share information via the repository about research outputs and tools needed for data re-use or validation.

Examples:

- Search data repositories on platforms like [OpenDOAR](#), [re3data](#)

- Code and software repositories on platforms like Github, [SoftwareHeritage](#), SoruceForge, Savannah, Launchpad
- Protocols on [Protocol Exchange](#)

[Open Source Initiative](#) (OSI) is a non-profit organisation dedicated to promoting and protecting open source software. It does so by defining and certifying open source software licences and supporting policies that benefit the open-source community. You can consult the website for [OSI approved licence examples](#).

Reproducibility of research materials (Mandatory) [↗](#)

Reproducible results are a key feature of HE projects, contributing to improved research and innovation outcomes, reduced waste, enhanced research quality, and greater public trust in scientific research.

! Note: Some of these recommendations below might be already mentioned in other sections.

Below, you can find some recommendations about the reproducibility aspect.

The Turing Way project illustration by Scriberia

1 - Document Your Methods Clearly:

- Make your research transparent detailing your methods, including experiments, data collection, and analysis.
- Keep it clear so researchers from different fields can replicate your work.
- Explain how you handle any negative results.
- Mention the measures and tools implemented during your research.

2 - Ensure Validity and Quality:

- Outline steps taken to ensure the validity and quality of your project's process and results, (e.g. peer review, independent testing, quality control mechanism).
- Implement version control systems (e.g. Git) to track changes in your code.
- Consider using tools (e.g. Docker) to package your software ensuring compatibility across different systems.
- Specify measures for robust statistical analysis (e.g. power of sample, robust experimental techniques, open software).

3 - Collaborative and Transparent Research Environment:

- Share your source code and algorithms openly on platforms like GitHub or GitLab that encourage collaboration, and synchronise with Software Heritage for a long-term archiving.
- Provide straightforward instructions for accessibility and (re)use.
- Enhance transparency including sample datasets and test run instructions for easier validation.
- Promote code reviews within your team and collaborate with peers.

4 - Produce Digital Copies of Results:

- Consider whether your project will produce a digital copy of your results (e.g. digital twins, virtual bodies, digital blueprints, etc.).

5 - Link Datasets to Publication:

- Link your datasets to your publication.

Example:

- How to Cite Datasets and Link to Publications:
https://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/publications/reports/guides/How_to_Cite_Link.pdf
- Sharing research data linked to publications:
https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Guide_Partager_les_donnees_web.pdf (in french):

Translated from the guide, "[Sharing research data linked to publications](#)"

For more detailed information, you can also consult these guides:

- [Guide for Reproducible Research](#) by Turing Way
- [Reproducibility in Science](#)

Share your research early and open (Recommended) [↗](#)

This section refers to making your research outputs accessible at the earliest stages of the research process.

- Share pre-registration of research plan, if possible, in a public repository to enhance credibility, public trust and reproducibility.

Some pre-registry repository examples:

- [OSF](#) registries: domain-general
- [AsPredicted](#): domain-general
- [Preclinicaltrials.eu](#): animal study protocols
- [PROSPERO](#): health and social care
- [Evidence in Governance and Politics \(egap\)](#): political sciences
- [Registry for International Development Impact Evaluations](#): social sciences

- Engage in transparent peer review processes, such as open peer review or post publication peer review, to enhance the quality and accountability of scholarly communication.

Example:

- Participate in open peer review initiatives on platforms like [Episciences](#), [Peer Community In](#) or [F1000Research](#), where reviews are openly accessible alongside published articles.

Preprint repositories examples:

- [OSF](#) preprints: discipline-specified
- [Preprints.org](#): multidisciplinary
- [arXiv](#): discipline-specified

Engaging with all actors (Recommended) [↗](#)

Involving citizens, civil society and other actors in your project is also recommended as part of the OS practices.

- Develop strategies to involve the general public in your research process, from data collection to analysis (e.g. web platforms, events, applications) implementing mechanisms for feedback and recognition for participants.
- Outline how citizen science will extend the reach and application of your research findings, if applicable. Describe the potential societal benefits.
- Collaborate with non-profit organisations or educational institutions to develop citizen science projects).
 - Ressources: e.g. [European Citizen Science Association](#) (ECSA)

Research Data Management (Mandatory) [↗](#)

According to [Science Europe](#), “research data management (RDM) refers to the handling of research data (collection, organisation, storage, and documentation) during and after a research activity. Good data management helps ensure that researchers share their data in a FAIR way (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)”

RDM is also one of the mandatory OS practices, but it should be discussed in the section below.

Research Data Management (RDM) and management of other research outputs - [1 page] / Data Management Plan (DMP) [↗](#)

! Note: It is important to note that the OS practices might overlap with RDM.

In this section, the main expected output is to provide a data management plan (DMP) that details how you will manage your research data. According to the [HE Programme Guide](#), the DMP is a “formal document that outline from the start of the project all aspects of the research data lifecycle, which includes its organisation and curation, and adequate provisions for its access, preservation, sharing, and eventual deletion, both during and after a project”.

In HE programs, DMPs are required for all projects that generate or reuse data. However, you are only required to submit a one-page preliminary DMP at the submission stage of your project, with a complete DMP to be provided later⁷.

Step 1: **Inclusion of RDM Work Package**

- Begin by adding a dedicated RDM work package to your grant agreement.⁸
- Name this work package "*Research Data Management*" to clearly emphasise its purpose.

Step 2: **Define Deliverable - Data Management Plan (DMP)**

- Associate a specific deliverable with the RDM work package, termed "DMP - Data Management Plan."
- This plan should be categorised under the "Data Management Plan" type.
- Set a due date for the DMP, specifying a deadline of 6 months into the project implementation.

Step 3: **Dissemination Level Selection**

- Decide on the dissemination level for your DMP—either “sensitive” or “public”.
- Opting for the latter means that the accepted DMP will be publicly accessible on the CORDIS page of your project, in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines.

Step 4: **Submission Deadline**

- Ensure timely submission of the DMP, meeting the specified deadline at the end of the 6th month of project implementation.

Step 5: **Crafting a Comprehensive DMP**

- Recognize that writing a robust DMP is intricately linked to the methodology of your research.⁹

⁷ Keep in mind that a DMP is a living document that should be updated regularly throughout the project.

⁸ This is a unique requirement for ERC projects under Horizon Europe.

⁹ While the HE provides templates, you have the flexibility to adapt it or use an alternative, ensuring coverage of the FAIR principles.

- Additionally, outline resource allocation and data security, and explain any restrictions on access to specific parts of the research data.

For more information about DMPs, you can consult this guide “[Guidelines for Data Management Plan within the Framework of Horizon Europe](#)¹⁰” produced by 'DatASaclay' of Université Paris-Saclay.

Below, you can find some recommendations related to RDM. As you can remark, these recommendations can also be applicable to DMPs.

Source: <https://dynamics.folio3.com/blog/what-are-the-three-main-goals-of-data-lifecycle-management-dlm/>

1. Data Management Planning:

- Develop a comprehensive DMP outlining how you will collect, document, store, and share research data throughout your project.
- Clearly define data formats, metadata standards, and data documentation protocols to ensure interoperability and reusability.
- Consider ethical, legal, and security issues related to data sharing and storage, and address them proactively in your DMP.

Example:

¹⁰ Brenel, M., Diallo, M., Mainali, S., Mercier, C., Shi, Z., & Suhan, S. (2023). Guidelines for Data Management Plan within the framework of Horizon Europe: RIA, IA, CSA, EIC Pathfinder, Cofund. (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10123889>

- Create a DMP using tools (e.g., [DMP Opidor](#), [DMP Online](#), [argos](#), [DS Wizard](#)), specifying data formats (e.g., CSV, XML), metadata standards (e.g., DataCite), and data storage options (e.g., institutional repository, domain-specific repository).

2. Data Collection and Documentation:

- Collect and document research data systematically, ensuring accuracy, consistency, and completeness.
- Include detailed descriptions of data collection methods, instruments used, and any associated calibration or validation procedures.
- Use version control to track changes to your data over time and maintain clear records of data provenance and lineage.

Example:

- Document experimental protocols, parameters, and instrumentation settings in lab notebooks or electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs). See the [Report produced by the French Committee for Open Science's Working Group on Electronic Lab Notebooks](#) presents lists of evaluation criteria, scoring grids for the solutions considered, and graphical representations to assist in the choice of a solution.
- Ensuring that data are recorded in a structured and standardised format followed by a README file.

3. Data Sharing and Access:

- Share research data as openly and widely as possible, following FAIR principles.
- Deposit your data in trusted repositories or data archives that provide persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) and ensure long-term preservation.
- Consider embargo periods or access restrictions only when necessary, and provide clear justifications for any limitations on data access.

Example:

- Deposit data in trusted repositories ensuring that datasets are findable and accessible to the research community.

4. Data Licensing and Attribution:

- Choose open licences, such as Creative Commons licences, to clearly specify how others can use, reuse, and redistribute your data. You can adapt these licences according to your needs in the project.
- Clearly attribute data sources, including your own, in publications, presentations, and other research outputs to facilitate proper citation and credit.
- Consider data citation standards and best practices to ensure that your data receive proper recognition and are cited appropriately by others.

Example:

- Licence your research data under a Creative Commons CC-BY licence, allowing others to share and adapt the data with proper attribution, and provide clear guidance on how to cite the data in publications.

5. Ethical and Legal Considerations:

- Ensure that your research adheres to ethical standards and respects participants' rights, especially in data sharing and collaboration.

Research ethics and integrity, as well as open science, have different focuses, which can sometimes send mixed messages to researchers. Research ethics and integrity often limit acceptable research practices, while open science aims to expand good practices by making research accessible and transparent. This does not mean they contradict each other, but their different perspectives can confuse researchers. Researchers might feel pressured to follow open science guidelines and also meet data protection requirements.

Since most researchers are not experts in open science or law, it can be difficult to understand and navigate these rules. This can lead to researchers either ignoring safeguards in favour of open science or avoiding open science due to fear of legal or ethical issues. Balancing these aspects is challenging and requires careful attention.

Recommendations:

- Obtain informed consent from participants for data collection and data sharing, anonymize sensitive information, and comply with relevant ethical guidelines and regulations.
- If your project employs personal and/or sensitive data, contact the Data Protection Officer.
- Contact Ethic Committees services in your university, if needed.
- For matters of scientific integrity, consult the [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#).

- Given the immense potential of artificial intelligence, the need for regulation initially emerged through proposals of ethical principles (which were notably detailed in the 2021 UNESCO recommendation). However, European law goes further, and the European Union regulation (AI Act) will govern the development of the most critical uses of artificial intelligence. Refer to [EU Artificial Intelligence Act](#).

6. Data Preservation and Long-Term Access:

- Ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of your research data by archiving them in trusted repositories or data centres.
- Follow established data preservation standards and practices to ensure data integrity, authenticity, and usability over time.
- Not all the data are destined to be archived, so get in touch with Archives services in your university to determine a proper long-term preservation plan and policies.

Example:

- Nakala repository propose long-term preservation with CINES (National Computer Center for Higher Education (CINES), based in Montpellier) on demand¹¹.
- The Qualitative Data Repository (QDR) commits to preserving deposited data for a minimum of 25 years and they are members of 'Data Preservation Alliance for the Social Sciences' network to ensure a continuity plan in case of cessation of activities.
- For others Examples about long-term preservation, please take a look at [discipline based data repository list](#) created by Collège Données de la recherche [In French]

! Note: Pay attention to the distinction between long-term archiving and storage!

¹¹ See more via <https://documentation.huma-num.fr/nakala-faq/#lors-de-la-demande-de-preservation-a-long-terme>

Part B - 'Impact'

2.2 *Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities* #@COM-DIS-VIS-CDV@#

At a minimum, address the following aspects:

- Plan for the dissemination and exploitation activities, including communication activities:⁴ Describe the planned measures to maximize the impact of your project by providing a first version of your 'plan for the dissemination and exploitation including communication activities'. Describe the dissemination, exploitation measures that are planned, and the target group(s) addressed (e.g. scientific community, end users, financial actors, public at large). Regarding communication measures and public engagement strategy, the aim is to inform and reach out to society and show the activities performed, and the use and the benefits the project will have for citizens. Activities must be strategically planned, with clear objectives, start at the outset and continue through the lifetime of the project. The description of the communication activities needs to state the main messages as well as the tools and channels that will be used to reach out to each of the chosen target groups.
- Strategy for the management of intellectual property, foreseen protection measures: if relevant, discuss the strategy for the management of intellectual property, foreseen protection measures, such as patents, design rights, copyright, trade secrets, etc., and how these would be used to support exploitation.

 All measures should be proportionate to the scale of the project, and should contain concrete actions to be implemented both during and after the end of the project.

1 - **Alignment between OS Practices and the Dissemination, Communication Plan:**

- Ensure that your OS practices described in the 'Excellence' section are compatible with your dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan.

2 - **Open Access and Early Sharing:**

- Recognize that open access and early sharing contribute significantly to knowledge dissemination, influencing the 'Impact' section of your proposal.
- Reference your envisaged practices from the 'Excellence' section in your dissemination and exploitation plan.

3 - **Considering Commercial Exploitation and Ownership (IPR):**

- Take into account potential commercial exploitation activities and ownership of results.
- Before making a research public, if there is commercial exploitation potential, be careful that sharing data won't compromise patent protection.
- Making research outputs publicly available online may impact commercial exploitation or violate Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). When uncertain, you can wait until the patent application is filed before publishing your research outputs. Once the embargo period is over, you can freely share your data => "Close as necessary"

According to European IP Helpdesk, “Horizon Europe rules state that intellectual property protection comes before open science obligations when protection and exploitation of project results would be adversely affected by making project results and data available in open access¹²”.

4 - Acknowledge Restrictions and Embargo Periods:

- Providing open access to certain research outputs may face restrictions or require embargo periods (e.g, patent protection).
- Ensure clarity and agreement on ownership among consortium members to facilitate open access after any necessary waiting periods.

5 - Data Papers

- Data papers inform the scientific community about the existence, originality, quality, and availability of a dataset. It highlights the work of its authors by explaining the importance of the generated data and their potential for reuse in future research.
- Mention how publishing data papers can influence your research and scholarly communication.

6 - Mentioning Datasets in the Publication

- Explain how citing datasets can change scholarly communication within your field, highlighting the importance of data transparency and accessibility.

7 - Engaging with Citizens Science, if Applicable

- Involving a larger and more diverse group of people can lead to a wider dissemination of research findings and results.

Part B - 'Quality and efficiency of the implementation'

Under the 'Capacity of Participant' and 'Consortium as a Whole' (Section 3), proposers should describe how the consortium brings together necessary (inter)disciplinary knowledge. They should show how this includes expertise and/or track record in OS practices.

Work plan and resources

¹² European Commission: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, European IP helpdesk – Your guide to open science in Horizon Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/943044>

3.1 Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages

Required sub-headings:

- Work Packages (WP) List (please include Table 3.1a);
- Description of Work Packages (please include Table 3.1b);
- Deliverables List (please include Table 3.1c);
- Milestones List (please include Table 3.1d);
- Recruitment Table per beneficiary (please include Table 3.1e);
- Individual Research Projects, including secondment plan (please include table 3.1f);
- Progress monitoring and evaluation of individual research projects;
- Implementation Risks (please include Table 3.1g);
- Recruitment strategy (including how the project will strive to adhere to the Code of Conduct for the recruitment of researcher);
- For DN-JD, joint admission, selection, supervision, monitoring and assessment procedures (if not applicable, please remove).

[MSCA DN Application Form](#)

1 - Include DMP:

- Ensure the inclusion of your DMP as a deliverable, assigning it to an associated work package.

Publish your DMP as a public deliverable, unless there are valid reasons for not doing so (e.g., legitimate interests).

2 - Incorporate Other Relevant RDM Activities:

- Identify and assess costs associated with various RDM activities.
- Consider including additional RDM activities.

The infographic features a blue header with a white checkmark icon and the text 'What to cost in?'. Below the header is a dark blue box containing an orange piggy bank icon on the left. To the right of the icon are two columns of text. The first column is titled 'Infrastructure costs' and lists: Digitisation, Storage, Licensing and Security, Sharing and Re-use, and Archiving. The second column is titled 'Skills costs' and lists: Data wrangling, Description and Documentation, Metadata generation, Formatting and Cleaning, and Consent and Anonymisation. The two columns are separated by the text '... and'.

O'Connor, R., Delipalta, A., & Jones, S. (2020). What will it cost to manage and share my data?. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4548344>

Capacity of participants and consortium as a whole [max. 3 pages] [↩](#)

The MSCA program is more focused on the participant aspect, whereas the ERC can also include the consortium aspect.

3.2. Quality, capacity and role of each participant, including hosting arrangements and extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise

Required sub-headings:

- Appropriateness of the research infrastructure and capacity of each participating organisation, as outlined in Section 4 (Participating Organisations), in light of the tasks allocated to them in the action;
- Consortium composition and exploitation of participating organisations' complementarities: explain the compatibility and coherence between the tasks attributed to each beneficiary/associated partner in the action, including in light of their experience; Show how this includes expertise in social sciences and humanities, open science practices, and gender aspects of R&I, as appropriate.
- Exceptional funding (if applicable)

[MSCA SE Application Form](#)

1 - Link participant's or consortium's expertise with OS practices

- Include a section describing the expertise and/or track record in OS practices that the consortium brings to the project.
- Demonstrate the connection between the consortium's capabilities and the intended OS practices.
- If OS is not applicable, demonstration of the consortium's open science track record and expertise is not required.

Budget

What	Description	Who can help you to define the costs
Open Access publication cost	Some journals charge an Article Processing Charges (APC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Check in the host institution the grant office and their financial support for cost▪ Ask the librarians support for assistance
Data curation in Open Science	The lifecycle of the data management is in this guide	Ask data stewards and librarians for assistance and support and involve them in your RDM work

[OS in the HE proposal](#)

Further Reading

- Siiri Fuchs, & Mari Elisa Kuusniemi. (2018). Making a Research Project Understandable - Guide for Data Documentation (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1914401>
- An Analysis of Open Data and Open Science Policies in Europe, SPARC Europe, 2019. https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/SPARC-DCC_Open-Data-and-Open-Science-Policies-in-Europe_v4.pdf
- RDMkit, <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>.
- OpenAIRE Guides: Guiding You in Open Science, <https://www.openaire.eu/guides>.
- Webinar: [A successful proposal for Horizon Europe: Scientific-technical excellence is key, but don't forget the other aspects](#) (21 April 2021)
- Brenel, M., Diallo, M., Mainali, S., Mercier, C., Shi, Z., & Suhan, S. (2023). Guidelines for Data Management Plan within the framework of Horizon Europe: RIA, IA, CSA, EIC Pathfinder, Cofund. (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1012388>
- Horizon Europe Programme Guide Version 4.1, 1 May 2024, https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
- Hadrossek, Christine, Joanna Janik, Maurice Libes, Violaine Louvet, Marie-Claude Quidoz, Alain Rivet, et Geneviève Romier. « Guide de bonnes pratiques sur la gestion des données de la Recherche », 2023, 105. <https://mi-gt-donnees.pages.math.unistra.fr/guide/00-introduction.htm> (In French)
- European Commission: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, European IP helpdesk – Your guide to open science in Horizon Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/943044>
- Giglia, E. (2021). A guide to Open Science in Horizon Europe (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5542376>

Source: Infographic created by Open science team, Ghent University Library

MSCA Evaluation Form

1. Excellence

The following aspects will be taken into account, to the extent that the proposed work corresponds to the description in the work programme:

- *[OPTION for MSCA Doctoral networks, Postdoctoral fellowships and Staff exchanges:* Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives (and the extent to which they are ambitious, and go beyond the state of the art).
- Soundness of the proposed methodology (including interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension and other diversity aspects if relevant for the research project, and the quality and appropriateness of open science practices).]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Doctoral networks* Quality and credibility of the training programme (including transferable skills, inter/multidisciplinary, inter-sectoral and gender as well as other diversity aspects).
- Quality of the supervision (including mandatory joint supervision for industrial and joint doctorate projects).]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Postdoctoral fellowships;* Quality of the supervision, training and of the two-way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host.
- Quality and appropriateness of the researcher's professional experience, competences and skills.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Staff exchanges:* Quality of the proposed interaction between the participating organisations in light of the research and innovation objectives.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA COFUND:* Quality and novelty of the selection / recruitment process for the researchers (transparency, composition and organisation of selection committees, evaluation criteria, equal opportunities, the gender dimension and other diversity aspects) and quality and attractiveness of the appointment conditions, including competitiveness of the salary for the standards of the hosting countries.
- Quality and novelty of the research options offered by the programme in terms of science, interdisciplinarity, inter-sectorality and level of international mobility. Quality of open science practices.
- Quality, novelty and pertinence of the research training programme (including transferable skills, inter/multidisciplinary, inter-sectoral and gender as well as other diversity aspects).
- Quality, novelty and pertinence of the supervision, career guidance and career development arrangements.]

[HE MSCA Evaluation Form](#), p. 4

2. Impact

The following aspects will be taken into account, to the extent that the proposed work corresponds to the description in the work programme:

- *[OPTION for MSCA Doctoral networks* Contribution to structuring doctoral training at the European level and to strengthening European innovation capacity, including the potential for:
 - a) meaningful contribution of the non-academic sector to the doctoral training, as appropriate to the implementation mode and research field
 - b) developing sustainable elements of doctoral programmes.]
- Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of researchers and contribution to their skills development.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Postdoctoral fellowships:* Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of the researcher and contribution to his/her skills development.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Staff exchanges:* Developing new and lasting research collaborations, achieving transfer of knowledge between participating organisations and contribution to improving research and innovation potential at the European and global level.
- Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives of staff members and contribution to their skills development.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA COFUND:* Strengthening human resources good practices at institutional, regional, national or international level, in particular through aligning the practices of participating organisations with the principles set out by the EU for human resources development in research and innovation.
- Credibility of the proposed measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of researchers and contribution to their skills development.]
- *[OPTION for all MSCA except Special needs allowances:* Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Doctoral networks, Postdoctoral fellowships and Staff exchanges:* The magnitude and importance of the project's contribution to the expected scientific, societal and economic impacts.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Special needs allowances:* Effectiveness of the proposed measures with respect to the work in the linked MSCA action.]

[HE MSCA Evaluation Form](#), p. 5

3. Quality and efficiency of the implementation

The following aspects will be taken into account, to the extent that the proposed work corresponds to the description in the work programme:

- *[OPTION for all MSCA except Special needs allowances:* Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Doctoral networks and Staff exchanges:* Quality, capacity and role of each participant, including hosting arrangements and extent to which the consortium as a whole brings together the necessary expertise.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Postdoctoral fellowships:* Quality and capacity of the host institutions and participating organisations, including hosting arrangements.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA COFUND:* Quality and capacity of the host institution(s) and participating organisations (where appropriate), including hosting arrangements and extent to which they bring together the necessary expertise to successfully implement the research training programme.]
- *[OPTION for MSCA Special needs allowances:* Appropriateness of the resources deployed.]

[HE MSCA Evaluation Form](#), p. 6

Open science

Open science is a general principle of the Horizon Europe programme, and a core principle of the ERC. The ERC is committed to the principle of open access to the published output of research, including, in particular, peer-reviewed articles and monographs. It also supports the basic principle of open access to research data and data-related products such as computer code, algorithms, software, workflows, protocols, electronic notebooks, or any other forms of research output. The ERC considers that providing free online access to all these materials can be the most effective way of ensuring that

¹⁴ This includes peer-reviewed book chapters and long-text publications such as monographs, edited collections, critical editions, scholarly exhibition catalogues, or PhD theses.

Under Horizon Europe, beneficiaries of ERC grants must ensure immediate open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications¹⁴ relating to their results as set out in the Model Grant Agreement used for ERC actions. Open access has to be provided with full re-use rights¹⁵. Beneficiaries must ensure that they or the authors retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with their open access requirements. Publishing costs can be considered as eligible costs provided that the publishing venue (e.g. journal, book) is fully open access.

In addition, beneficiaries of ERC grants funded under this Work Programme will be covered by the provisions on research data management as set out in the Model Grant Agreement used for ERC actions. In particular, whenever a project generates research data, beneficiaries are required to manage it in line with the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability as described by the FAIR principles initiative¹⁶, and establish a data management plan within the first six months of project implementation. Open access to research data should be ensured under the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. These provisions are designed to facilitate access, re-use and preservation of the research data

¹⁵ For monographs and other long-text formats, commercial re-use and derivative works may be excluded as specified in the [General Model Grant Agreement for ERC Actions under Horizon Europe](#).

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Evaluation criterion and procedure

Evaluation criterion and elements

For Starting, Consolidator, Advanced, and Synergy grants, **scientific excellence is the sole criterion of evaluation.**

The panels will primarily evaluate:

- the ground-breaking nature, ambition, and feasibility of the research project.

At the same time, the panels will evaluate:

- the intellectual capacity, creativity, and commitment of the Principal Investigator(s), with a focus on the extent to which the Principal Investigator(s) has the required scientific expertise and capacity to successfully execute the project.

In the case of a Synergy Grant application, the peer reviewers will need to see that the collaborative working arrangements between the Principal Investigators, described as part of the research methodology, can ensure scientific excellence.

Additional considerations

During the evaluation, the peer review panels will take into account the phase of the Principal Investigator's transition to independence, diverse research career

paths and particularly noteworthy contributions to the research community, as well as possible breaks in the research career of the applicant and the effects of major life events or pandemic restrictions on the applicant's progression as a researcher. Applicants may include relevant additional information on their research careers to provide context to the evaluation panels when assessing their research achievements and peer recognition (see "Proposal description" above). Synergy Grant Principal Investigators applying as part of a group for a Synergy Grant will be evaluated according to their individual career stage.

In the context of the Covid-19 outbreak, applicants may mention in their research proposal (Curriculum Vitae) any specific situation caused by the pandemic that had a negative impact on their CV or track record.

In general, projects wholly or largely consisting in the collation and compilation of existing material in new databases, editions, or collections are unlikely to constitute ground-breaking or 'frontier' research in themselves, however useful such resources might be to subsequent original research. Such projects are therefore unlikely to be recommended for funding by the ERC's panels.

Plagiarism detection software may be used to analyse proposals submitted to the ERC.

The detailed evaluation elements applying to the excellence of the research project and the Principal Investigator are set out below (see “Evaluation Elements applying to Excellence”).

Evaluation procedure⁵⁷

For Starting, Consolidator, and Advanced Grants

A single submission of the proposal will be followed by a **two-step evaluation**. The evaluation will be conducted by means of a structure of high-level peer review panels as listed in Annex 1. The panels may be assisted by independent external experts working remotely.

The applicant Principal Investigator can request during the electronic proposal submission that up to three specific persons should not act as an evaluator in the evaluation of their proposal⁵⁸.

At step 1, the Extended Synopsis and the Principal Investigator's CV and Track Record will be assessed.

Based on the outcome of the evaluation at step 1, up to 44 proposals per panel will be retained for step 2 of the evaluation.

At step 2, the entire research proposal⁵² will be assessed.

The allocation of the proposals to the various panels will be based on the expressed preference of the applicant Principal Investigator (see section

⁵⁷ Procedural aspects that are not specified in this Work Programme are established in the ERC Rules of submission and evaluation under Horizon Europe.

“Proposal description” above). Proposals may be allocated to a different panel with the agreement of both Panel Chairs concerned.

The panel to which a proposal is allocated may request additional reviews by appropriate members of other panel(s) or additional remote evaluators.

The ERC welcomes interdisciplinary research proposals. Proposals of this type are evaluated by ERC's regular panels with the appropriate external expertise.

Principal Investigators, whose proposals are retained for step 2 of the evaluation, will be invited for an interview to present their proposal to the evaluation panel meeting.

For Synergy Grants

A single submission of the proposal will be followed by a **three-step evaluation**, including interviews. The evaluation will be conducted by means of a structure of dedicated panels. The panels may be assisted by independent external experts working remotely.

The applicant Corresponding Principal Investigator can request, on behalf of the group, during the electronic proposal submission, that up to four specific persons

⁵⁸ The persons identified may be excluded from the evaluation of the proposal concerned, as long as it remains possible to have the proposal evaluated.

Evaluation Elements applying to Excellence

1. Research Project

Ground-breaking nature, ambition, and feasibility

Starting, Consolidator, Advanced, and Synergy Grants

Ground-breaking nature and potential impact of the research project

To what extent does the proposed research address important challenges?

To what extent are the objectives ambitious and beyond the state of the art (e.g. novel concepts and approaches or development between or across disciplines)?

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[ERC Work Program 2024](#), p. 36

Scientific Approach

To what extent is the outlined scientific approach feasible bearing in mind the ground-breaking nature and ambition of the proposed research (based on the Extended Synopsis)?

*To what extent does the proposal go beyond what the individual Principal Investigators could achieve alone (**for Synergy Grants**, based on the Extended Synopsis)?*

*To what extent do the Principal Investigators succeed in proposing a combination of scientific approaches that are crucial to address the scope and complexity of the research questions to be tackled (**for Synergy Grants**, based on the Extended Synopsis)?*

To what extent are the proposed research methodology and working arrangements appropriate to achieve the goals of the project (based on the research proposal)?

To what extent are the proposed timescales, resources, and PI commitment adequate and properly justified (based on the research proposal)?

[ERC Work Programme 2024](#), p. 37

2. Principal Investigator(s)

Intellectual capacity and creativity

Starting, Consolidator, Advanced, and Synergy Grants

To what extent has/have the PI(s) demonstrated the ability to conduct ground-breaking research?

To what extent does/do the PI(s) provide evidence of creative and original thinking?

To what extent does/do the PI(s) have the required scientific expertise and capacity to successfully execute the project?

Synergy Grant Group

Synergy

To what extent does the Synergy Grant Group successfully demonstrate in the proposal that it brings together the know-how – such as skills, experience, expertise, disciplines, teams – necessary to address the proposed research question (based on the Extended Synopsis)?